

Original Article

Education Financing in India: Navigating the Neo-Liberal Shift

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Manuscript ID:

JRD -2025-170216

ISSN: 2230-9578

Volume 17

Issue 2

Pp. 80-91

February 2025

Submitted: 11 Jan. 2025

Revised: 20 Jan. 2025

Accepted: 23 Feb. 2025

Published: 28 Feb. 2025

Abstract:

The focus of this paper is on analysing the changing nature of sources of education finance in India. The onset of a wave of liberalisation and privatisation in the last quarter of 20th century has shifted the policy orientation of developed and developing countries wherein more importance is accorded to private sector while the state's role is shrinking in every economic activity including education. In line with the global trends, India has progressively been withdrawing its funding in social sector including education and providing more space to private service provider since the 1980s. Using various indicators related to different sources of educational financing, it is observed that privatisation wave is taking place at all levels of education- elementary, secondary and higher. The pace is fastest in case of higher education. Further, inter-state comparison of the increasing role of household level financing of education indicates that, in general, economically well-off states are leading the poor states in this trend. The shift in the sources of education finance (from public to private) may have far reaching implications for the economic development and smooth social transformation especially in a heterogeneous society like India.

Keywords Words: Education, education finance, public funding, privatisation, higher education.

I. Context of the study

Education holds the key to inclusive growth owing to the links between education and earnings. There are huge socio-economic returns associated with education and these returns increase with an increase in the level of education. Private average global returns to an additional year of schooling are 9 percent a year (Psacharopoulos and Patrinos 2018). Labor market inequalities are determined to a large extent by differences in level of education (Card, Domnisoru and Taylor, 2018). Education helps an individual to have better access to better opportunities in the labor market irrespective of her socio-economic background. In this way, education helps in upward socio-economic mobility of individuals and also prevents their downward mobility (Cheema, 2018). For these reasons public provision of quality education is considered crucial for equitable access and affordability of education for all (Card, Domnisoru and Taylor, 2018). Making education accessible and affordable for all, the Government of India has been paying special attention since the first Five-year plan by adopting a sectoral approach wherein elementary education received topmost priority. Article 45 of the Indian constitution passed in 1950 stated that "the state shall endeavour to provide, within a period of ten years from the commencement of this Constitution, for free and compulsory education for all children until they complete the age of fourteen years." Further, various commissions and committees have been set up by the government from time to time for promoting educational attainment in the country. The Education Commission (1964-1966) popularly known as Kothari Commission analysed in detail the past trends of education financing in India and emphasised that public spending on education must be raised to 6 per cent of gross national product (GNP) by 1986 to adequately develop education in India. Following the recommendations, the National Policy on Education was announced in 1968. Besides re-emphasising that public investment on education should be 6 per cent of GNP, the policy also emphasised promoting equality of access and

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How to cite this article:

Singh Jatinder, M. D. (2025). Education Financing in India: Navigating the Neo-Liberal Shift. *Journal of Research and Development*, 80-91.

Access this article online

providing free education upto class 10. It also highlighted that increased funding and organisational support was required for increasing the access to education and equity in its distribution. Further, during the last couple of decades, India has announced a series of schemes and programmes (District Primary Education Programme, Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, Right to Education Act, Mid-day Meal scheme, National Curriculum Framework etc) aimed at expanding elementary education. These policies and programmes have facilitated in improving literacy rate in general and ensuring equal access to all sections of the society in particular (NIEPA, 2018). The desired success of various policies and programmes has been constrained by an inadequate financial support. It is well acknowledged in the literature that education sector in India is facing a huge financial crunch (Gill, Singh and Brar, 2010; Brar, 2018). Public spending on education in India is much less than advanced countries. For instance, expenditure of advanced countries on education has remained above 5-7 per cent of GDP (UNESCO 2018). India is not only spending less than advanced countries, even within BRICS countries India's spending on education has remained least. For instance, India spent 3.2 per cent of GDP on education in 2013 whereas Brazil was spending 5.3 per cent, Russia 4.4 per cent, China 4.3 per cent, and South Africa 6.9 per cent (BRICS 2015). The financial crunch to the education sector has become more severe with change in policy orientation initiated in the early 1980s and scaled in the early 1990s. This shift from a controlled regime towards a liberal policy regime has paved way for commercialisation of education. As a result, education is now considered as a marketable commodity to be supplied at cost plus basis. The approach paper of 10th, 11th and 12th five year plans clearly marked the need and paved the way for private sector and demand side financing of education.

In this context, this study aims at analysing the emerging structure of education financing in India. Further, the paper attempts to understand the changing importance of different sources of educational financing both at national level and across states. Paper sets the context by discussing about the importance of public financing of education. For empirical analysis, paper uses secondary information collected from various government publications. The major secondary sources include Selected Educational Statistics, Analysis of Budgeted Expenditure, Unified – District Information System for Education, and All India Survey on Higher Education. Paper is divided into four sections including introduction. Section 2 develops a theoretical understanding on the significance of public expenditure on education by using theoretical and empirical literature. Section 3 provides a discussion on empirical analysis carried-out in the paper. Last section summarises the major findings emerging from the analysis.

II. Public expenditure on education: Why so important?

Investment in education is a key factor in promoting human capital formation which is in turn considered as one of the most important inputs for economic development (Romer 1986; Lucas 1988; Ranis, Frances and Alejandro 2000). Education helps in improving learning and skill formation which leads to improvement in individual productivity and life-time earnings and eventually improves the productivity at national level. The twin contribution of education in building capabilities at individual level as well as national level puts education high on the public investment agenda. Every developed and developing country makes budgetary provisions for investment in education. In the words of Soubbotina and Sheram (2000: 36) "The national stock of human capital and its rate of increase are critical to a country's level and rate of economic development, primarily because human capital is the most important determinant of a country's ability to produce and adopt technological innovations..... Differences in public spending on education (relative to GDP) across countries reflect differences in government efforts to increase national stocks of human capital". Further, the differences in the public spending on education across countries accumulate and reflect itself in the form of different levels of economic development. It indicates that public financing of education in a country plays an important role in determining future trajectories of growth and development. The role of public funding in educational development is considered critical due to the fact that investment in education causes positive externalities on the economy as well as society (Friedman, 1955). The spillover effects of such investment leads to social and economic development by creation of knowledge and human capital development. Alternatively, since education promotes human capital development, it is in every country's interest to consider it as a public good and make investment for its generation, expansion, equal distribution and accumulation. If left to individual pursuits, investment in education will certainly remain at under-optimum level as is the case with most of the goods with positive externalities and more so in case of an imperfect labour and capital market of a developing country like India. An individual will be unable to calculate the divergence between private and societal benefits of the investment and hence education is likely to be under-provided. Public financing of education is also important for controlling the persistence of long-term inequalities (Pew Charitable Trusts, 2012). Long-term inequalities are considered to be inversely related to economic mobility which is in turn positively related to education. Evidence indicates that increase educational attainment increases the extent of economic mobility (Haskins, Holzer and Lerman 2009). A study by Pew Charitable Trusts (2012) argues that "the wage premium associated with a college degree rose dramatically during the past generation, and increased returns on education directly translate into upward absolute mobility gains." Besides, education plays a key role in promoting economic mobility of desired nature by overcoming various socio-economic barriers viz. caste, class, religion, gender, region etc. on the path towards upward economic mobility (Cheema, 2018). Therefore, access to education plays a key role in determining the nature and extent of economic mobility. The better and wider the access to education, the greater will be the extent of upward economic mobility of desired nature.

Therefore, it serves as a means to eliminate inequalities in the long term (Grawe 2008; Cheema 2018). Hence, it is important to provide equality of access to education and opportunities based on that education. If access to education remains unequal, inequalities may continue to persist and become even sharper in the long-term. For these reasons and more, most of the countries in the world pitch for public financing of education and provide free primary education, at the least, and also subsidise hugely the higher education (Soubbotina and Sheram 2000). In the absence of state driven provision of educational facilities, universal access to quality education is no less than a dream for any country.

III. Empirical Analysis

Empirical analysis has been conducted both at the national level and the state level. First part of the analysis provides a discussion on the government spending on education with reference to various national and state level aggregates. Second part analyses the trends in extent of privatisation of education at the school level and at higher education level. Further, a few cases of state level universities have been discussed to provide a broader overview about the economic health of public universities in the wake of changing policy environment.

III.1. Trends in public spending on education

Table 1 presents the trends on combined expenditure of centre and states on education as percentage of GDP and total budgeted spending on all sectors. These are commonly used indicators to understand the commitment of the government towards education. It is observed that expenditure on education as a percentage of GDP in India has increased over the years. Since 1951-52, expenditure by education and other departments has increased from 0.64 per cent to 4.38 per cent of GDP in 2016-17. The expenditure by education department remained highest (3.37 per cent) in the year 1990-91 whereas expenditure by education and other departments remained highest (4.14 per cent) in the year 2000-01. Similarly, the share of educational spending in total budget has been witnessing an upward trend with some fluctuations (Table, 1). It varied between 3.57 per cent and 12.01 per cent of total budget during 2000-01 to 2016-17.

It is worth noticing that the rising expenditure on education is not evenly distributed across various levels of education viz. elementary, secondary, university and higher, adult and technical (Table 1A in annexure). Level-wise distribution of expenditure indicates that public expenditure on education at all levels except for elementary education has witnessed a consistent decline.

Table 1: Public Expenditure on Education by Education and Other Departments

Year	Percentage of GDP		Percentage of total budgeted spending	
	Expenditure by Education Department	Expenditure by Education & Other Departments	Expenditure by Education Department	Expenditure by Education & Other Departments
1951-52	0.64	0.64		
1960-61	1.48	1.48		
1970-71	2.11	2.11		
1980-81	2.59	2.98		
1990-91	3.37	3.84		
2000-01	3.25	4.14	8.81	10.83
2005-06	2.88	3.34	3.57	4.27
2006-07	2.92	3.48	9.15	11.36
2007-08	2.74	3.40	8.8	10.86
2008-09	2.88	3.56	8.9	10.96
2009-10	3.11	3.95	9.24	11.68
2010-11	3.22	4.05	10.15	12.72
2011-12	3.09	3.82	12.01	14.84
2012-13	3.01	3.70	10.45	12.82
2013-14	2.97	3.84	10.53	13.56
2014-15	2.90	4.07	10.08	14.07
2015-16	2.93	4.27	9.65	13.94
2016-17	3.03	4.38	10.01	14.33

Source: Analysis of Budget Expenditure on Education (Various years), MHRD, Government of India, New Delhi.

Increase in expenditure on elementary education in the post reform period should be seen in terms of policy emphasis of the national government and international agencies. The government has initiated various schemes and programmes during the 1990s and the early years of 21st century (District Primary Education Programme, Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, Right to Education Act, Mid-day meal scheme, National Curriculum Framework etc.) aiming at universalization of primary and elementary education. Given this, a large share of public funding for education has always gone to the expansion of elementary education. The disaggregation of total spending on education between the centre and the states indicates that the contribution of states has always dominated the total public expenditure on education. Combined spending of all states varied between 2.15 per cent to 2.74 per cent of GSDP during 2001-02 to 2016-17. Irrespective of a number of centrally funded schemes announced by union government since 2000, the

spending of union government on education in India could not cross 1 per cent of GDP. The trends are further worsening as the spending of the central government education department has started falling since 2010-11. It slipped from 0.72 per cent in 2010-11 to 0.47 per cent in 2016-17 (Figure, 1).

Figure 1: Trends in States' and Centre's Spending on Education by Education Department (% GDP)

Source: Same as Table 1.

The larger contribution of states for educational development is an outcome of the constitutional amendments over time. Education was considered to be the sole responsibility of the state till 1976. It affected the inter-state equality in expansion of education owing to the differences in economic capacities of states. The 42nd Constitutional Amendment brought education under the concurrent list. Accordingly, education became the responsibility of both the centre and the states. After this amendment, the centre government has continuously directed resources for the expansion of education (Jha and Singh 2013). Irrespective of continuous increase in the expenditure on education, the total spending till date remains far below the target provided by the first education commission way back in 1960s (Tilak 2007).

Table 2: Quartile-wise distribution of states in terms of spending on education (% of GSDP)

Quartile	2005-06	2010-11	2014-15	2016-17 (BE)
First	Assam (6.46), Bihar (5.99), HP (4.95), Rajasthan (3.94), Uttaranchal (5.35)	Assam (4.9), HP (4.91), J&K (5.25), Uttaranchal (8.01)	AP (3.65), Assam (7.37), Bihar (7.48), HP (4.48), J&K (5.52)	Assam (5.33), HP (4.07), J&K (4.05), MP (3.96), UP (3.97)
Second	Jharkhand (3.46), Kerala (3.24), MP (3.37), UP (3.56)	Bihar (4.07), Jharkhand (3.41), Orissa (3.49), Rajasthan (3.31), UP (3.54)	Orissa (3.58), Rajasthan (3.38), Uttaranchal (3.54), UP (3.54)	Bihar (2.72), Jharkhand (3.16), Odisha (3.55), Rajasthan (3.29), Uttarakhand (2.85)
Third	J&K (3.2), Karnataka (3.06), Maharashtra (2.92), Orissa (3.07), Tamil Nadu (2.61)	Karnataka (2.92), Kerala (2.84), MP (3.06), Maharashtra (2.88), West Bengal (2.87)	Haryana (2.72), Jharkhand (3.07), Kerala (3.12), MP (3.28), West Bengal (3.31)	AP (2.66), Haryana (2.20), Kerala (2.51), Punjab (2.24), West Bengal (2.60)
Fourth	AP (2.25), Gujarat (2.12), Haryana (2.36), Punjab (2.6), West Bengal (2.48)	AP (2.41), Gujarat (2.02), Haryana (2.51), Punjab (2.2), Tamil Nadu (2.55)	Gujarat (2.24), Karnataka (2.67), Maharashtra (2.56), Punjab (2.45), Tamil Nadu (2.40)	Gujarat (1.75), Karnataka (1.84), Maharashtra (2.04), Tamil Nadu (2.13), Telangana (1.48)
Coefficient of Variation (CV)	35.98	40.24	41.06	33.84

Source: Same as Table 1. Note: Figures in parenthesis indicate percentage share.

As observed from figure 1, the state governments are taking up a major responsibility of educational development in India. The combined spending of all states on education reached to 2.56 per cent of GSDP in 2016-17. But given the socio-economic, geographic and political differences across the states, uniformity in spending is seldom expected. The state level analysis indicates huge variations across the states in terms of spending on education (Table 2). The value of CV remained high and further it has consistently increased overtime. In 2005-06, value of CV was 35.98 which increased to 41.06 in 2014-15. Based on the expenditure on education as percentage of GSDP, the states are classified into four quartiles, the first quartile indicating the top 25 per cent states in terms of their spending and fourth quartile being the bottom 25 per cent states. It is interesting to note that rich states in India in general are directing fewer resources towards educational development as compared to the poor states (Table 2). For instance, states like Punjab, Gujarat, Haryana, Karnataka, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu etc. are economically well-off but these states have always remained in third or fourth quartile during 2005-06 to 2016-17. On the other hand, poor states like

Bihar, Assam, Rajasthan, Uttaranchal, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir, Uttar Pradesh etc. remained in top two quartiles. Further, the expenditure in rich states shows a declining trend. The emerging trends of declining public spending on education across the rich states may be attributed to different set of factors. The most important could be the wave of privatisation of education in the post reform period. As globalisation has increased returns to education, demand for education has seen a steep rise in the contemporary times. This factor may have induced private investors to exploit the emerging situation. Besides, reduced fiscal space of central government for social sector in the wake of liberalisation and privatisation may be one of the reasons. Given this, an attempt has been made to understand the extent and pace of privatisation of education across states in India.

III.2. Extent of private financing of education in India

Unlike public spending on education, we don't have direct information on private financing of education in India. Due to non-availability of direct information, the extent of private financing of education is analysed indirectly by using indicators such as number and growth of private educational institutes, share of private institutes in total number of institutes, enrollment in private institutes etc. Besides, we also try to understand the extent of hidden privatization of educational institutes since a large number of public funded higher education institutes are continuously witnessing a decline in the size of public grant and meeting their growing financial needs by raising their own resources.

Table 3: Management-wise distribution of elementary schools across states (in '000)

	2003-04		2010-11		2015-16			2016-17		
	Govt.	Private	Govt.	Private	Govt.	Private	Other	Govt.	Private	Other
Andhra Pradesh	73.7 (87.16)	10.9 (12.84)	79.4 (76.43)	24.5 (23.57)	73.1 (72.17)	27.1 (26.72)	1.1 (1.11)	73.7 (71.63)	28.2 (27.46)	0.9 (0.90)
Assam	37.9 (96.17)	1.5 (3.83)	44.4 (82.38)	9.5 (17.62)	50.1 (76.10)	7.8 (11.90)	7.9 (12.01)	50.2 (75.68)	8.2 (12.41)	7.9 (11.91)
Bihar	51.5 (98.59)	0.7 (1.41)	67.9 (99.42)	0.4 (0.58)	71.4 (89.08)	3.5 (4.34)	5.3 (6.58)	71.6 (88.53)	3.9 (4.79)	5.4 (6.69)
Chandigarh	0.1 (42.07)	0.1 (57.93)	0.1 (62.64)	0.1 (37.36)	0.1 (57.21)	0.1 (39.80)	0.0 (2.99)	0.1 (57.71)	0.1 (39.80)	0.0 (2.49)
Chhattisgarh	33.3 (93.88)	2.2 (6.12)	46.4 (90.37)	4.9 (9.63)	44.4 (87.54)	6.1 (12.03)	0.2 (0.43)	44.4 (86.79)	6.5 (12.76)	0.2 (0.46)
Gujarat	31.8 (91.38)	3.0 (8.62)	33.6 (82.35)	7.2 (17.65)	33.8 (76.83)	10.2 (23.17)	0.0 (0.01)	33.8 (75.95)	10.7 (24.04)	0.0 (0.01)
Haryana	11.0 (97.29)	0.3 (2.71)	15.0 (74.07)	5.2 (25.93)	14.6 (65.56)	6.8 (30.69)	0.8 (3.75)	14.4 (63.52)	7.4 (32.36)	0.9 (4.12)
Himachal Pradesh	14.3 (95.62)	0.7 (4.38)	15.1 (86.74)	2.3 (13.26)	15.4 (85.36)	2.6 (14.63)	0.0 (0.01)	15.5 (85.12)	2.7 (14.87)	0.0 (0.01)
Jammu & Kashmir	-	-	22.2 (81.86)	4.9 (18.14)	23.3 (81.63)	5.2 (18.36)	0.0 (0.01)	23.3 (81.30)	5.4 (18.69)	0.0 (0.01)
Jharkhand	21.3 (96.55)	0.8 (3.45)	40.5 (93.75)	2.7 (6.25)	40.4 (85.24)	2.6 (5.45)	4.4 (9.31)	39.3 (84.23)	2.3 (4.87)	5.1 (10.91)
Karnataka	43.8 (85.06)	7.7 (14.94)	46.6 (78.30)	12.9 (21.70)	45.6 (73.79)	16.2 (26.17)	0.0 (0.04)	45.0 (72.58)	16.9 (27.33)	0.1 (0.08)
Kerala	4.9 (40.61)	7.1 (59.39)	5.0 (38.43)	7.9 (61.57)	4.6 (27.79)	10.2 (62.13)	1.7 (10.09)	4.9 (29.46)	10.0 (60.93)	1.6 (9.61)
Madhya Pradesh	75.1 (87.02)	11.2 (12.98)	112.0 (82.48)	23.8 (17.52)	114.5 (80.28)	26.5 (18.55)	1.7 (1.17)	114.3 (79.62)	27.6 (19.20)	1.7 (1.18)
Maharashtra	60.6 (78.37)	16.7 (21.63)	69.0 (70.94)	28.3 (29.06)	67.3 (68.52)	30.4 (30.94)	0.5 (0.55)	66.9 (63.78)	37.4 (35.59)	0.7 (0.63)
Orissa	46.7 (95.25)	2.3 (4.75)	57.2 (89.01)	7.1 (10.99)	58.5 (84.77)	8.5 (12.38)	2.0 (2.85)	57.8 (83.74)	8.8 (12.73)	2.4 (3.54)
Punjab	9.7 (97.82)	0.2 (2.18)	20.2 (86.33)	3.2 (13.67)	20.5 (71.20)	7.2 (24.89)	1.1 (3.91)	20.5 (71.47)	7.3 (25.56)	0.9 (2.97)
Rajasthan	68.0 (87.06)	10.1 (12.94)	77.5 (74.73)	26.2 (25.27)	70.7 (65.47)	34.9 (32.31)	2.4 (2.22)	67.9 (64.43)	34.8 (33.05)	2.7 (2.52)
Tamil Nadu	35.4 (76.97)	10.6 (23.03)	36.1 (65.64)	18.9 (34.36)	38.2 (66.39)	19.2 (33.30)	0.2 (0.31)	38.3 (66.04)	19.2 (33.16)	0.5 (0.79)
Uttar Pradesh	109.2 (81.34)	25.0 (18.66)	151.5 (75.35)	49.5 (24.65)	161.3 (65.60)	80.4 (32.69)	4.2 (1.71)	161.4 (63.50)	82.2 (32.34)	10.6 (4.17)
Uttarakhand	15.2 (86.83)	2.3 (13.17)	17.3 (77.54)	5.0 (22.46)	17.5 (73.99)	5.8 (24.46)	0.4 (1.56)	17.5 (73.98)	5.8 (24.36)	0.4 (1.66)
West Bengal	54.7 (91.79)	4.9 (8.21)	79.1 (90.09)	8.7 (9.91)	82.7 (86.43)	9.8 (10.19)	3.2 (3.38)	83.0 (86.08)	10.4 (10.79)	3.0 (3.13)
Average of selected states	798.2 (87.09)	118.3 (12.91)	1036.1 (80.35)	253.3 (19.65)	1048.0 (74.53)	320.9 (22.82)	37.2 (2.64)	1043.9 (73.27)	335.8 (23.57)	44.9 (3.15)

Source: NIEPA (2018). Note: Figures in brackets indicate the percentage of total number of schools in respective year.

The distribution of elementary schools governed by different types of management in India is presented in Table 3. Educational institutes are generally governed by four types of managements namely government, government aided, private and others. In this analysis, private unaided and private aided institutes are combined together owing to non-availability of separate data for some years. On an average, the presence of private schools at elementary level has been on the rise. The share of private schools has increased from 12.91 per cent in 2003-04 to 23.57 per cent in 2016-17 (Table 3). In the recent years (2015-16 to 2016-17), absolute number of government schools has also recorded downfall whereas the number of private schools has been continuously increasing since 2003-04 (Table 3). State-wise analysis indicates a considerable variation. More than 90 per cent of total elementary schools in a large number of states were state owned in the early years of 21st century. For instance, out of 19 states in 2003-04, 10 recorded more than 90 per cent presence of government-owned schools at elementary level. But there is a big change in management of elementary schools in 2016-17. All the ten states recording above 90 per cent government schools recorded below 90 per cent presence of government owned schools in the later period. Besides, other states with below 90 per cent government schools initially have moved to further lower categories (Table 3A in annexure). For instance, no state was present in the category 61-70 per cent in 2003-04, but in 2016-17 four states have moved into this category from categories above 70 per cent.

Table 4: Elementary-level enrolment in Management-wise schools across states (in '00000)

	2003-04		2006-07		2010-11		2015-16		
	Govt.	Private	Govt.	Private	Govt.	Private	Govt.	Private	Others
Andhra Pradesh	79.65 (77.80)	22.73 (22.20)	73.33 (64.85)	39.74 (35.15)	61.91 (57.16)	46.40 (42.84)	53.67 (50.56)	51.32 (48.34)	1.17 (1.10)
Assam	35.89 (96.17)	1.43 (3.83)	45.58 (84.04)	8.65 (15.96)	40.98 (79.68)	10.45 (20.32)	41.40 (76.22)	9.55 (17.59)	3.36 (6.19)
Bihar	111.32 (99.26)	0.83 (0.74)	148.73 (98.36)	2.48 (1.64)	195.65 (99.50)	0.98 (0.50)	215.48 (91.96)	8.96 (3.82)	9.88 (4.22)
Chandigarh	0.70 (67.04)	0.35 (32.96)	0.83 (66.39)	0.42 (33.61)	1.04 (70.10)	0.45 (29.90)	1.02 (64.52)	0.55 (34.85)	0.01 (0.63)
Chhattisgarh	34.10 (89.29)	4.09 (10.71)	36.84 (87.81)	5.11 (12.19)	38.08 (82.20)	8.25 (17.80)	32.81 (73.62)	11.60 (26.02)	0.16 (0.36)
Gujarat	58.65 (88.87)	7.35 (11.13)	60.84 (80.68)	14.57 (19.32)	59.17 (72.64)	22.28 (27.36)	58.16 (63.98)	32.73 (36.01)	0.01 (0.01)
Haryana	17.34 (95.73)	0.77 (4.27)	21.08 (84.57)	3.84 (15.43)	20.87 (61.51)	13.06 (38.49)	16.64 (44.59)	19.71 (52.82)	0.96 (2.59)
Himachal Pradesh	9.80 (90.17)	1.07 (9.83)	8.71 (80.51)	2.11 (19.49)	7.46 (72.07)	2.89 (27.93)	5.80 (61.04)	3.70 (38.95)	0.00 (0.00)
Jammu & Kashmir	0.00	0.00	10.25 (62.95)	6.03 (37.05)	12.13 (60.73)	7.85 (39.27)	10.25 (55.18)	8.32 (44.81)	0.00 (0.00)
Jharkhand	32.98 (96.51)	1.19 (3.49)	59.98 (94.38)	3.57 (5.62)	55.99 (86.32)	8.87 (13.68)	47.29 (72.51)	9.30 (14.26)	8.63 (13.24)
Karnataka	59.30 (75.54)	19.20 (24.46)	55.23 (70.01)	23.66 (29.99)	46.25 (60.32)	30.43 (39.68)	42.49 (50.95)	40.90 (49.03)	0.02 (0.02)
Kerala	11.94 (37.36)	20.02 (62.64)	12.29 (36.12)	21.73 (63.88)	10.76 (31.32)	23.59 (68.68)	8.89 (22.16)	29.02 (72.32)	2.21 (5.52)
Madhya Pradesh	81.44 (79.32)	21.24 (20.68)	110.65 (72.88)	41.17 (27.12)	106.54 (69.38)	47.03 (30.62)	79.79 (62.33)	46.90 (36.63)	1.33 (1.04)
Maharashtra	82.04 (59.79)	55.17 (40.21)	79.98 (52.08)	73.58 (47.92)	74.22 (46.16)	86.56 (53.84)	59.49 (37.08)	100.19 (62.45)	0.76 (0.47)
Orissa	54.95 (95.98)	2.30 (4.02)	46.20 (93.76)	3.08 (6.24)	56.54 (88.74)	7.18 (11.26)	50.54 (79.86)	10.24 (16.18)	2.51 (3.96)
Punjab	12.42 (99.82)	0.01 (0.08)	22.13 (81.91)	4.89 (18.09)	21.69 (70.25)	9.18 (29.75)	20.72 (52.30)	16.52 (41.68)	2.39 (6.02)
Rajasthan	71.11 (81.41)	16.24 (18.59)	86.62 (69.50)	38.00 (30.50)	71.04 (59.79)	47.79 (40.21)	62.66 (50.78)	58.92 (47.74)	1.82 (1.48)
Tamil Nadu	52.40 (57.53)	38.69 (42.47)	50.85 (52.01)	46.92 (47.99)	42.74 (43.67)	55.12 (56.33)	41.71 (45.15)	50.48 (54.65)	0.18 (0.19)
Uttar Pradesh	194.83 (76.86)	58.65 (23.14)	230.92 (71.80)	90.71 (28.20)	196.90 (61.67)	122.37 (38.33)	166.03 (45.58)	188.77 (51.82)	9.46 (2.60)
Uttarakhand	9.88 (77.04)	2.94 (22.96)	10.79 (76.38)	3.34 (23.62)	9.41 (58.71)	6.62 (41.29)	7.57 (44.21)	9.07 (52.96)	0.48 (2.83)
West Bengal	102.28 (79.69)	26.06 (20.31)	86.36 (64.73)	47.06 (35.27)	134.38 (92.92)	10.25 (7.08)	111.94 (86.71)	11.43 (8.86)	5.72 (4.43)
Average of Selected States	1113.03 (78.75)	300.33 (21.25)	1258.18 (72.36)	480.68 (27.36)	1263.75 (69.01)	567.60 (30.99)	1134.36 (59.59)	718.17 (37.73)	51.07 (2.68)

Source: Same as Table 3. Note: Figures in brackets indicate the percentage of total number of schools in respective year.

The above trends related to increased privatisation of education get better reflected in Table 4. Out of total schools, private schools accounted for around 24 per cent of total elementary schools in the recent years. But in terms

of enrollment, the share of private schools increased from 21.25 per cent in 2003-04 to 37.73 per cent in 2015-16 (Table 4). Further, in absolute terms, enrollment in public schools has initially increased from 1113 lakh in 2003-04 to 1264 lakh in 2010-11 and then declined to 1134.4 lakh in 2015-16. On the other hand, enrollment in private elementary schools has increased by 2.4 times during 2003-04 to 2015-16.

State-wise analysis also revealed that the share of government schools has declined whereas this decline was apportioned as gain by the private schools. However, a huge variation has been noticed across the states in terms of share of government and private schools in enrollment. In 2003-04, less than 1 per cent students were enrolled in private schools in Punjab whereas this percentage went upto 43 per cent in 2015-16. In 2003-04 there were 6 states who recorded more than 90 per cent enrolment in government schools at elementary level but in 2015-16, 5 states were found in categories lower than 90 per cent. There is no single state which has not observed a movement to a lower category in terms of percentage share of government schools in enrolment. In 2003-04, Kerala was the only state to have less than 50 per cent share of government schools in enrolment but in 2015-16, 4 other states have joined this category. In terms of percentage decline in government school enrolment during 2003-04 to 2015-16, Punjab and Haryana are the ones observing highest decline, with Haryana observing a decline of more than 50 per cent. Further, 6 states (Haryana, Kerala, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh and Uttarakhand) have reported more than 50 per cent enrolment in private schools at the elementary level (Table, 4). Another 5 states have reported 40 to 50 per cent of total enrolment at elementary level in private schools. Another important thing to be noticed is that, in economically poor states, government schools are still serving more than 80 per cent of total enrolled students at the elementary level. Bihar is the only state which has recorded more than 90 per cent of total elementary enrolment in government schools; it is followed by West Bengal (86.71 per cent).

It is clear that the role of private schools is increasing at all levels of education in India over time. Further, there is a positive association between level of education and participation of private sector as reflected in disaggregated analysis (Table 4A in annexure). As the level of education is increasing from elementary to higher secondary, percentage share of private schools is also increasing.

With a few exceptions, privatisation of school education is positively related to economic health of the state and literacy rate in the state. Households in economically well-off states generally have the required capacity to afford private education. Since growth of private education sector in a state is governed by profitability, they would prefer to flourish more in states having higher paying capacity for education. The private service providers operate only on full cost-plus recovery mode. Services are offered to only those who pay for the services. Further, higher the literacy rate in a state, higher is the value given to education. Households in a more literate society are expected to be ready to pay more money as compared to their counterparts in a less literate society as the former group will put higher value on education.

III.3. Financing of Higher Education

As observed in the previous analysis, composition of public funding across different levels of education revealed that more than 80 per cent of total expenditure on education is accounted for by just elementary and secondary education (Table 2A in annexure). Remaining 20 per cent is distributed among other levels of education including higher education. It is observed that the share of higher education in total public spending remained fluctuating at around 12 to 13 per cent during 2004-05 to 2014-15 (Table 2A in annexure). Bhushan (2010) reported two phases of public expenditure in case of higher education in India (i) 1951-52 to 1979-80 and (ii) 1980-81 to 2003-04. It was reported that the second phase observed a drastic decline in public expenditure on higher education. Growth rates of plan and non-plan expenditure on education in case of centre and states were 17 per cent and 15 per cent respectively during 1951-52 to 1979-80 which declined to 10 per cent and 11 per cent in the following phase (1980-81 to 2003-04). Author further pointed out that public expenditure per student at constant prices has increased both in case of elementary and secondary education whereas downfall has been witnessed in case of higher education during 1993-94 to 2007-08. The low and declining level of public sector funding in the phase of growing demand for higher education in India has strongly paved the way for private entry.

To analyse the extent of privatisation in higher education, we have compiled the information on different types of institutes over the years (Table 5). During 2010-11 to 2017-18, the number of universities and institutes of national importance has increased from 621 to 903. In 2010-11, public funded universities and institutes constituted around 70 per cent of the total universities and institutes which declined to around 61 per cent in 2017-18. Disaggregated information brings forth that share of each type of public institute/university has declined, in general, during the reference period whereas the share of state private universities has increased by 2.07 times from 14.01 per cent to 29.13 per cent during 2010-11 to 2017-18. In terms of CAGR, this growth amounts to 17.12 per cent which is far ahead than growth of any other type of institute.

Table 5: Changing Composition of Indian Higher Educational Institutes

	2010-11		2017-18	
	Number	%	Number	%
Central University	42	6.76	46	5.09
Government Deemed University	40	6.44	33	3.65
Government Aided Deemed University	-	-	10	1.11
Institution of National Importance	59	9.50	101	11.18
State Public University	294	47.34	365	40.42
State Private University	87	14.01	263	29.13
Private Deemed University	91	14.65	80	8.86
Others	8	1.29	5	0.55
Total	621	100.00	903	100.00

Source: GOI (2013 and 2018).

Table 6 further reveals that private unaided colleges are flourishing and observing high growth in the period when government and private aided colleges are observing an absolute decline in their numbers and share in enrolment. Private unaided colleges have grown from 59 per cent (2010-11) to 64.69 per cent (2017-18) of total number of colleges. Similarly, their enrolment share has increased from 37.02 per cent to 46.67 per cent during the same period. Decline in the number and share of even private aided colleges is most surprising and lead us to strongly assert that privatisation in education sector is coming in a big way.

Table 6: Composition of Colleges and Distribution of Enrolment (in %)

	2010-11		2017-18	
	% share in total no. of colleges	% share in total Enrolment	% share in total no. of colleges	% share in total enrolment
Government	26.79	39.20	21.96	32.71
Private Aided	14.21	23.78	13.35	20.62
Private Unaided	59.00	37.02	64.69	46.67
Total Private (Aided + Unaided)	73.21	60.80	78.04	67.29

Source: Same as Table 5.

State-wise trends indicate that privatisation of higher education is common among all the states but the nature and the pace of privatisation differ significantly across the states. The pace of privatisation of higher education in some states namely Punjab, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Gujarat, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand and Karnataka remained much faster as compared to other states like Assam, Bihar and Odisha during 2010-11 to 2017-18. Further the composition of students enrolled in different types of institutes indicates that the share of private institutes is growing significantly. Enrolment share of such institutes in some states has reached to an alarming extent viz. Andhra Pradesh (77.36 %), Uttar Pradesh (72.48 %), and Tamil Nadu (61.64 %). It implies that expansion of higher education in India is significantly based on household financing/private financing of education.

State Universities and Public Funding:

Besides direct privatisation of state-run universities and colleges, the public funding to these institutes has also been continuously shrinking. A majority of the state-run universities are passing through a serious financial crunch and under pressure to generate revenue from own sources (Agarwal, 2006; Brar, 2018). Thus, self-financed courses have become very much prevalent in public funded higher educational institutes. Bhushan (2010) estimated discipline-wise average fee of self-financing courses in Central, State and Deemed universities. According to Bhushan, on an average, a student pays Rs. 19274 in central university, Rs. 31388 in state university and Rs. 46510 in deemed university for a self-financed course.

The evidence suggests that tuition fees as a share of total revenue of universities declined from 36.8 per cent to 13.8 per cent between 1950-51 and 1983-84 (Tilak 1993). Contrarily, it has been rising after the introduction of new policy regime. Agarwal (2006) estimates that on an average, 49.7 per cent of total funding for higher education is coming from private sources. The share of fee remained 19 per cent in case of government institutes, 38 per cent in private aided institutes and 100 per cent in private unaided institutes (Agarwal 2006). The situation is worrisome in case of state universities. More than 50 per cent of their operating budget (Madras University -50.4%, Bangalore University -63.7%, Panjab University -50.4 %) in 2004-05 was financed by tuition fee (Jha and Singh 2013). Recent evidence on state universities in Punjab indicates alarming trends. In case of Punjabi University Patiala, state grant was Rs. 86.91 crore which constituted just 23.21 per cent of total annual budget of the university in terms of average of three financial years 2013-14, 2014-15 and 2015-16 (Brar 2018). 20 to 25 years back, the state grant used to constitute more than three fourth of the total expenses of the university (Kaur and Singh, 2017). Similarly, in case of Guru Nanak

Dev University, Amritsar, state grant was just Rs. 50 crore in 2016-17 which formed around 21 per cent of total annual expenses of the university.

The above analysis strongly indicates that privatisation of education at all levels is taking place in a very big way. Comparison at different levels of education reveals that this trend is much stronger at the level of higher education as compared to other levels. Based on these evidences, one can argue that education in India especially higher education is not getting desired priority from state. These trends have far reaching implications for social inclusion especially in a country like India which is socially very heterogeneous in nature.

VI. Conclusion and Discussion

The focus of this paper is to understand the changing sources of education finance in India in the post reform period. Empirical analysis indicates that the public sector spending on education in India has observed a downfall in the post reform period. The shrinking role of public financing of education has caused new sources of education finance, including household funding, to fill in the vacuum. Further, there is huge variation in the public funds dedicated to different levels of education (elementary, secondary and higher). The information on disaggregate spending at different levels of education reveals that the main focus of public investment in education is on elementary education. Almost half of the public funds on education are dedicated to elementary education. The investment on secondary and higher education is declining. It has resulted in greater privatisation of education at secondary and higher level.

Another important observation remains that inter-state variation is huge in terms of the magnitude of privatisation of education financing. Generally, economically well-off states are observing greater degree of private funding in education sector as compared to poor states.

Privatisation is taking two forms- first, completely private universities and institutes are coming up and second, reliance on tuition fees for running the state funded universities is increasing in the wake of steep reduction in public funding to such universities. Facing huge financial crunch, state funded universities are forced to rely more and more on self-financed courses. Evidence indicated that around 80 per cent of annual budgets of various universities are constituted by tuition fees or other fees. This trend is increasing the cost of education for students and making its access difficult for weaker sections of society.

Increased privatisation of education financing has serious implications for the socio-economic progress of the country. Private sector is expected to serve only those with paying capacity. The exclusion of poor mass from accessing the education may result in higher socio-economic inequalities since unequal access is ought to promote upward economic mobility of only those having access to education and keep others out of its purview. Given the increasing control of private sector on education services, inequalities in the distribution of education services can only be expected to increase further.

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Annexure

Figure 1A: Trends in States’ and Centre’s Spending on Education by Education and other Departments (% GDP)

Table 1A: Level-wise Combined Budgeted Expenditure (Revenue) of the Centre and States (% of GDP)

Years	Elementary Education	Secondary Education	University & Higher Education	Adult Education	Technical Education	Total
1990-1991	1.78	1.24	0.77	0.05	-	3.84
1991-1992	1.76	1.26	0.75	0.04	-	3.80
1995-1996	1.72	1.17	0.65	0.02	-	3.56
2000-01	1.88	1.25	0.81	0.01	-	3.95
2001-02	1.75	1.10	0.63	0.02	-	3.50
2002-03	1.76	1.15	0.69	0.02	-	3.61
2005-06	1.61	0.86	0.65	0.01	0.27	3.34
2011-12	1.71	0.98	0.62	0.01	0.51	3.82
2014-15	1.82	0.98	0.65	0.01	0.57	4.03
2014-15	1.81	0.98	0.57	0.01	0.70	4.07
2015-16(R.E)	1.79	1.01	0.65	0.01	0.80	4.27
2016-17(B.E)	1.82	1.05	0.64	0.01	0.87	4.38

Source: Same as Table 1.

Table 2A: Level-wise Public Expenditure on Education

States	2004-05					2014-15				
	Elementary Education	Secondary	Higher education	Tech Education	others	Elementary Education	Secondary	Higher education	Tech Education	Others
Andhra Pradesh	50.71	30.78	13.65	3.37	1.49	40.25	38.41	15.83	4.24	1.26
Assam	58.91	27.36	10.73	0.98	2.02	57.04	27.09	13.19	1.05	1.64
Bihar	54.68	20.36	20.51	1.2	3.26	64.27	14.88	15.4	0.56	4.89
Chhattisgarh	71.8	15.09	11.08	1.78	0.26	58.34	35.98	3.82	1.59	0.26
Gujarat	54.82	31.48	8.95	2.92	1.82	62.88	25.05	7.02	3.01	2.04
Haryana	50.33	33.89	11.94	3.1	0.74	58.61	25.19	11.16	4.93	0.11
Himachal Pradesh	54.33	38.14	6.08	0.71	0.74	58.42	32.99	7.25	0.89	0.45
Jammu & Kashmir	45.79	37.2	13.73	1.96	1.32	41.86	42.24	13.07	2.6	0.23
Jharkhand	71.44	13.93	10.43	3.99	0.22	66.32	13.61	16.65	2.79	0.63
Karnataka	57.21	27.1	11.63	2.24	1.82	52.21	29.59	12.82	3.56	1.81
Kerala	43.1	35.68	14.81	5.05	1.36	36.66	38.97	17.04	6.21	1.12
Madhya Pradesh	68.42	15.72	12.35	3.11	0.39	59.87	28.07	9	1.93	1.13
Maharashtra	43.97	42.58	9.18	3.3	0.98	44	40.56	10.68	4.3	0.46
Orissa	57.12	25.93	15.31	1.1	0.53	52.37	28.82	16.73	1.05	1.03
Punjab	24.59	64.14	9.14	1.28	0.85	31.62	57.41	8.65	1.65	0.67
Rajasthan	57.06	33.56	6.79	0.93	1.67	56.78	35.66	5.53	0.77	1.27
Tamil Nadu	42.22	38.12	11.25	2.8	5.61	38.08	40	9.98	4.99	6.95
Uttaranchal	45.75	42.2	7.34	3.98	0.73	43.93	46.33	5.66	2.68	1.39
Uttar Pradesh	57.87	30.73	8.52	1.7	1.18	72.11	19.96	6.33	0.71	0.88
West Bengal	37.68	48.22	11.84	0.85	1.42	37.88	47.74	10.57	2.02	1.78
Total States	50.62	34.25	11.01	2.43	1.69	51.95	32.7	10.75	2.67	1.93
Total (States & Uts)	50.14	34.75	10.86	2.5	1.75	51.75	32.77	10.69	2.76	2.03
Total Centre	58.67	10.86	16.01	11	3.47	51.28	14.62	20.21	12.34	1.55
Grand Total	51.52	30.89	11.69	3.87	2.03	51.65	29.06	12.63	4.72	1.93

Source: Same as Table 1.

Table 3A: Share of Government in total elementary schools across states

Range (in %age)	% age of government schools		Range (in %age)	% age points change in government schools 2003-04 to 2016-17
	2003-04	2016-17		
Less 50	Kerala	Kerala	Less than 5	West Bengal
61-70	-	Haryana, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu	5 to 10	Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, Bihar
71-80	Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu	Punjab, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Uttarakhand, Assam, Gujarat, Madhya	11 to 15	HP, Tamil Nadu, Kerala, Orissa, Jharkhand,

		Pradesh		Karnataka, Uttarakhand, Maharashtra, Gujarat
81-90	UP, Karnataka, Uttarakhand, Rajasthan, AP, MP	J&K, Orissa, Jharkhand, HP, West Bengal, Chhattisgarh, Bihar	16-20	Andhra Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Assam
91-95	Gujarat, WB, Chhattisgarh, Orissa		21 to 30	Rajasthan, Punjab
96 and above	HP, Assam, Jharkhand, Haryana, Punjab, Bihar		Above 30	Haryana

Source: Based on Table 3.

Table 4A: Share of government elementary schools in total enrolment across states

Range (in %age)	% age of students enrollment in government schools		Range (in %age)	% points change in enrollment 2003-04 to 2015-16
	2003-04	2015-16		
Less 50	Kerala	Kerala, Maharashtra, Uttarakhand, Haryana, Tamil Nadu, UP	Less than 5	
51-60	Tamil Nadu, Maharashtra,	AP, Rajasthan, Karnatha, Punjab, J&K	5 to 10	Bihar, J&K
61-70	-	HP, MP, Gujarat	11 to 15	TN, Kerala
71-80	Karnataka, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Andra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, West Bengal	Jharkhand, Chhattisgarh, Assam, Orissa	16-20	Chhattisgarh, Orissa, MP, Assam
81-90	Rajasthan, Gujarat, Chhattisgarh, HP	West Bengal	21 to 30	Maharashtra, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Gujarat, Andra Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh
91-95	-	Bihar	31 to 40	Rajasthan, UP, Uttarakhand
96 and above	Haryana, Orissa, Assam, Jharkhand, Bihar, Punjab		41 to 50	Punjab
			51 and above	Haryana

Source: Based on Table 4.

Table 5A: Level-wise distribution of Enrollment across different types of Schools in India (%age)

	Management	Elementary	Secondary	Higher Secondary	All Levels
2014-15	Government	60.16	44.16	35.35	55.55
	Government Aided	8.01	22.12	24.85	11.62
	Private Unaided	29.20	32.52	38.71	30.55
	Others	2.62	1.20	1.10	2.28
	Total Enrolment (in Nos.)	197666909	38301599	23501798	259470306
2016-17	Government	58.62	44.33	35.66	54.22
	Government Aided	7.79	21.36	25.14	11.54
	Private Unaided	30.74	33.11	38.37	31.84
	Others	2.86	1.20	0.83	2.41
	Total Enrolment (in Nos.)	189887015	38823854	24397536	253108405

Source: Same as Table 3.